

EuroGO-SHIP
Enhancing ocean observations

Science case for EuroGO-SHIP: Numerical modelling

Deliverable 4.1

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1. Description

This deliverable reports on the achievements of Task 4.1 of WP4, the science case of the EuroGO-SHIP Project. The analyses conducted focus on how expected improvements in data quality and coverage following the implementation of a EuroGO-SHIP research infrastructure (RI) will enable a better assessment of trends in ocean nutrient changes, deoxygenation and acidification. These are key marine health indicators as defined in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive. Here, effects of improved data quality as well as temporal coverage are quantified in terms of their impacts on the Trend Detection Time (TDT), a statistical metric that quantifies the number of years of data that are necessary to robustly detect a trend in a time series data set.

2. Introduction

The EuroGO-SHIP project develops a concept for a European Research Infrastructure (RI) for hydrography, to support very high-quality measurements of ocean physical and biogeochemical properties from research vessels. These include properties like ocean salinity and velocity, dissolved oxygen and inorganic carbon chemistry, inorganic nutrients and transient tracers. Such measurements are essential for understanding the ocean's role in local and global climate and ecosystems, and thus society's need for hydrographic data is growing. Currently many observations are made on a nation-by-nation or even institution-by-institution basis, producing data of variable quality in a fragmented way. The EuroGO-SHIP RI would address gaps in facilities and best practices, enabling the European hydrographic community to increase the quality, traceability, and availability of hydrographic data.

WP4 of EuroGO-SHIP gathers scientific input and conducts consultations with stakeholders to support the conceptualization of a new EuroGO-SHIP RI. Task 4.1 is the science case of the WP4 and has the objective to use numerical model output to quantitatively assess improvements in detecting signals associated with eutrophication and ocean acidification in the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) domain that will be brought about with the implementation of this RI.

In this report eutrophication is specifically quantified in terms of changes in nutrient concentrations and deoxygenation, while ocean acidification is quantified in terms of changes in H^+ ion concentrations instead of pH (more details are in Section 4). These three measurable properties would be covered by the EuroGO-SHIP RI. Changes in these properties influence the quality of seawater and impact both marine-economy and human health through the deterioration and reduction of areas suitable for resource extraction and other human activities in the oceans. Accurate monitoring of these properties is essential to optimize resources and minimize the impacts of human activities on marine systems. Such monitoring would entail obtaining high quality data that would allow us to efficiently and robustly quantify the variability and trends in these properties at regional scale.

2.1. Accuracy of marine measurements – in theory and practice

Ensuring data accuracy guarantees the inter-comparability of observations collected by different research teams, and a high confidence in estimated trends and natural variability. Standard operating procedures (SOPs) have been developed to ensure the quality and accessibility of observational data (Dickson et al., 2007; Hood et al., 2010; Becker et al., 2020). These manuals gather all the specific procedures, analytical methods, and protocols for the use of certified reference materials (CRMs; Dickson et al., 2003; Aoyama et al., 2012) required before, during, and after sampling. By following the Global Ocean Ship-based Hydrographic Investigations Program (GO-SHIP) repeat hydrography manual (Hood et al., 2010), one should achieve measurement accuracy of 0.002 in salinity, 0.5% in oxygen, between 1 % and 3% in the macronutrients (nitrate, phosphate and silicate), and 0.005 in pH. However, these procedures are often not followed in full such that inaccurate and imprecise observational data remain an issue in many regions. The disparity of the data quality lie in lack of either equipment or, expertise, training and implementation of best practice, between countries or even institutions, leading to differences in standardization and calibration and even to the use of various units for the same ocean property.

The accuracy normally achieved in practice is routinely evaluated in GLODAPv2 (Global Data Analysis Project version 2, Olsen et al., 2016, Lauvset et al., 2024), a global synthesis effort for hydrographic data. GLODAP subjects data from hydrographic surveys to extensive quality control, such as cross-over analysis and comparison with multilinear regression and neural network generated estimates to determine data inter-consistency. Data identified as significantly biased are adjusted before publication in the final data product. The GLODAP team has identified a set of minimum adjustment limits, these are smallest data biases that are possible to identify and adjust with reasonably certainty: 0.005 in salinity, 1 % in oxygen, 2 % in nitrate, 2 % in silicate, 2 % in phosphate, 4 $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ in dissolved inorganic carbon, 4 $\mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ in total alkalinity, and 0.01–0.02 in pH (depending on region). Of all the data currently included in GLODAPv2 (1108 cruises from 1972-2021), some 10 - 50%, depending on year of collection and variable, are found biased beyond these limits (see for example Figure 8 of Lauvset et al., 2024).

Time series exhibit long-term trends as well as cyclic and random changes (e.g., extreme events), where the two latter can be defined as background natural variability. Therefore, any change should reflect the real evolution of the marine system, not artifacts resulting from differences in sampling methodologies and frequencies, or biased data. Isolating a trend signal with confidence in the presence of background natural variability, depends on our ability to reliably detect long-term unidirectional signals enveloped in natural variability. Thus, this report focuses on the capability for improved trend detection achieved by the enhancement of data quality that is expected through the implementation of a EuroGO-SHIP infrastructure concept. We selected a statistical metric that allows quantification of the length of time series necessary to distinguish the trend from the natural variability, namely Trend Detection Time (TDT).

2.2. Objectives and scope of this deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable is to report on the results and recommendations of Task 4.1, Science case for EuroGO-SHIP.

The main objectives are:

- Goal 1: Understanding whether it is possible to take better advantage of existing sampling opportunities
- Goal 2: Assessing the benefits of improving data quality for our ability to detect trends
- Goal 3: Provide scientific output to support the description of regional observational needs.

2.3. Report Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1. Descriptive summary.
- Section 2. Introduction: background, opening note of the method and objectives.
- Section 3. Description of relevant key marine health indicators, and regions of interest.
- Section 4. Data and statistical metrics: brief description of the model et the origine of the reanalyzes, and the statistical approach and experiments conducted.
- Section 5. Goal 1: Length of the time series needed to detect an accurate trend of each indicator, and TDT estimation following temporal sub-sampling and data perturbation, in the Mediterranean Sea (subsection 5.1), the Black Sea (subsection 5.2), and the Baltic Sea (5.3).
- Section 6. Goal 3: Concluding scope and recommendations.

3. Processes and Regions of interest

3.1. Processes

To achieve the objectives of Task 4.1, we have targeted ocean properties that correspond to the key marine health indicators in the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) that contributes to the ambition of the European Green Deal. The main goal of this Directive is to achieve Good Environmental Status of European marine waters by maintaining a good balance between exploitation and preservation of marine resources. It includes eleven qualitative descriptors such as climate change, biological activity, and eutrophication. These help individual nations assess environmental status using key indicators, such as acidification, nutrient change, and deoxygenation, which are covered in this report.

- Acidification: Identifying acidification is one of the indicators used to monitor the environmental status describing climate change. Seawater acidification is a response

to human-induced rapid increase of atmospheric CO₂, by the uptake of the CO₂ by the sea and resulting reduction of calcium carbonate availability. These rapid chemical changes may cause wide-ranging impacts on marine ecosystems, by disturbing biological activities, such as coral reef-building and primary productivity. Additionally, changes in marine ecosystems can impact the global carbon cycle and diminish the ocean's ability to absorb more atmospheric CO₂, further exacerbating climate change.

- **Eutrophication:** Human activities, mainly agriculture and sewage discharge, release compounds of nitrogen and phosphorus into the rivers flowing to the sea. The nutrient enrichment of seas leads to biodiversity loss, favors the proliferation of harmful algae and the development of phytoplankton, which exacerbates the decline in oxygen due to the degradation of organic matter. The effects of eutrophication are reflected in the economic losses to human society caused by changes in fishing capacity and tourism activity in response to the deterioration of water quality.
- **Deoxygenation:** The decline in ocean oxygen concentrations is the combined result of ocean warming and eutrophication. For warming, it is the decline in solubility as well as increased residence times of waters in the inner ocean, resulting from increased stratification, that leads to deoxygenation. For eutrophication, increased anthropogenic nutrient supply fosters primary productivity in surface waters, which increases the sinking of degradable organic matter (OM) into the benthic layers, and leads to significant oxygen (O₂) consumption through aerobic microbial respiration (degradation) of OM. In the seas, deoxygenation can be used as an indicator of eutrophication. Deoxygenation leads to the reduction of the marine habitats

3.2. Regions

The analyses carried out in task 4.1 are focused on the Mediterranean Sea, the Black Sea, and the Baltic Sea. These marginal seas and epicontinental shelves represent a significant economic resource for the countries that border them. Although their respective ecosystems differ, these seas share dense human coastal population and are involved in various economic activities that result in high anthropogenic pressures.

3.2.1. Mediterranean Sea

The Mediterranean Sea is often viewed as a miniature version of the global ocean, offering valuable insights into both oceanographic and climatic processes and has been flagged as a hotspot for climate change (Giorgi, 2006). The geomorphology of this semi-enclosed sea gives rise to complex physical dynamics with a distinctive thermohaline circulation and permanent or semi-permanent sub-basin gyres. It is supplied with freshwater, nutrients and biomass by several large rivers with extensive catchment areas, resulting in mesotrophic to eutrophic conditions and heavy pollution along the coast, while offshore areas experience oligotrophic conditions increasingly toward the south, and extra-oligotrophic conditions eastward. Although several rivers flow into it, the hydrological cycle of the Mediterranean Sea is

responsible for its status as a concentration basin, since evaporation exceeds the sum of precipitation, riverine inputs and influxes through the Strait of Dardanelles resulting in highly saline seawater.

Figure 1: Bathymetry of the Mediterranean Sea

3.2.2. Black Sea

The Black Sea is challenging to assess, as it receives freshwater and sediments from three major European rivers: the Danube, Dnieper, and Don, across about twenty countries in Europe and Asia Minor. With ample river discharge, and precipitation exceeding annual evaporation, the Black Sea shows a positive annual water balance and can be defined as a dilution basin. The basin contains a series of cyclonic and anticyclonic mesoscale eddies embedded within the cyclonic general circulation and is characterized by a permanent pycnocline generated by freshwater input and the relatively saline Mediterranean inflow. This stratification generates an oxygen deficiency below 200 m depth, which contrasts with the oxygen-rich surface waters. The bottom waters are therefore oxygen-depleted and enriched in hydrogen sulfides and ammonia, which result in loss of marine life in about 90 % of the volume of the Black Sea. The oxygenated surface layer, on the other hand, is considered mesotrophic to eutrophic in both the northwest coastal sector and in the bordering Seas of Azov and Marmara.

Figure 2: Bathymetry of the Black Sea

3.2.3. Mediterranean-Black Sea Marine System (MBMS)

Despite the positive water balance of the Black Sea, the overall annual freshwater balance of the Mediterranean-Black Sea Marine System is negative, due to the large evaporation from Mediterranean Sea, which is compensated by the influx of water from the Atlantic Ocean, through the Strait of Gibraltar. Its predominantly poor trophic status contrasts with a high level of biodiversity, hosting over 10,000 marine species, which has earned it the designation of Biodiversity Hotspot by the United Nations Environment Programme, which designates environments characterized by both exceptionally high levels of endemism and critical levels of habitat loss, and it is thus on them that conservation efforts mainly focus (UNEP-MAP RAC/SPA, 2010).

3.2.4. Baltic Sea

The Baltic Sea is a semi-enclosed and non-tidal shelf sea in contact with the waters of the Atlantic Ocean by exchange with the North Sea through the Danish Strait. This exchange, however, is limited to episodic inflows of dense and oxygen-rich water, called Major Baltic Inflow events (MBI). The episodic nature of the inflows, in conjunction with fluvial discharges of surface freshwater, make the Baltic Sea a permanently stratified brackish water body with low oxygen conditions below 60 m depth. Within the central open regions (Bornholm Basin, Gotland Basin, Gulf of Finland), hypoxia is perennial, while it is seasonal at the entrance (Danish Straits), and occurs only episodically at coastal sites such as Limfjorden, because of meteorological and climatic factors as well as nutrients supply. Anthropogenic nutrient discharges are now considered the main driver of the increase in hypoxic conditions in the Baltic Sea over the last 50 to 100 years, as well as proliferation of harmful species that further exacerbate hypoxia through their degradation and ultimately sustain eutrophication in a 'vicious cycle'. Furthermore, climate change along with enhanced thermal stratification act to worsen this situation.

Figure 3: Bathymetry of the Baltic Sea

4. Data and methods

4.1. Data: Reanalyzes output

In line with the EuroGO-SHIP concept of sharing facilities, within task 4.1, we have relied on Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) reanalysis data products. CMEMS offers different services, one of whose objectives is to provide consistent retrospective data records (reprocessing and reanalysis) that are informative on the global ocean and European regional seas states (Le Traon et al., 2019). Reanalyzes are powerful datasets, by using observation data assimilation to constrain numerical models during the computation, they provide 4D fields that correspond to the best estimate of the ocean state (Escudier et al., 2021). These temporally and spatially full and relatively unperturbed data, were used within task 4.1 as the 'known-truth' for long term change and variability of ocean properties. Oxygen and nutrient data are used as is. However, pH data are transformed into hydrogen ion concentration (H^+) ion concentration (according to the definition of pH in equation 1), following the recommendations of Fassbender and co-authors (2021). The pH is a logarithmic measure of H^+ concentration and gives a relative idea of changes in H^+ concentration, each unit of change in pH corresponds to a change in H^+ by a factor of ten. It is therefore possible to obtain the same change in pH for different changes in H^+ concentration, depending on the initial pH of the seawater. Evaluating changes in H^+ is therefore preferable, for better comparability across regions.

$$pH = -\log_{10}([H^+])$$

.1

This study has been conducted using E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information, further details related to the model configurations and validation can be found in the documentation provided by CMEMS.

4.1.1. Mediterranean Sea model

The Mediterranean Sea biogeochemical reanalysis product (Figure 1) at 1/24° of horizontal resolution (ca. 4 km) and 125 vertical levels (MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004) covers the period from January 1999 to December 2020 with a monthly mean output produced by means of the MedBFM3 model system (runs by OGS, Italy; Teruzzi et al., 2021). MedBFM3, includes the transport model OGSTM v4.0 coupled with the biogeochemical flux model BFM v5 and the variational data assimilation module (3DVar-Bio v2.1; Salon et al., 2019, Teruzzi et al., 2019, 2018, 2014) for surface chlorophyll. MedBFM3 is coupled off-line with the CMEMS Mediterranean Sea physical reanalysis system (MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004 product runs by CMCC; Escudier et al., 2021) which provides forcing fields at a daily frequency for 21-year integration (i.e., currents, temperature, salinity, diffusivities, wind and solar radiation). This means that only the biogeochemical processes are simulated, while the physical variables resulting from the physical reanalyses are read to force tracer transport, dependency of biochemical kinetics on the temperature, and air-sea interactions. The ESA-CCI database of surface chlorophyll concentration (CMEMS-OCTAC REP product) is assimilated with a weekly frequency (Cossarini et al., 2021).

4.1.2. Black Sea model

The Black Sea biogeochemical reanalysis (Figure 2) at 1/40° of horizontal resolution (ca. 2.5 km) and 59 vertical levels (BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_007_005) covers the period from January 1992 to December 2022 with a monthly mean output produced by means of the NEMO-BAMHBI model system (runs by the MAST/ULg Production Unit, Belgium; Grégoire et al., 2020). NEMO-BAMHBI, includes the transport model NEMO v4.2 coupled with the Biogeochemical Model for Hypoxic and Benthic Influenced areas (BAMHBI, Grégoire et al., 2008; Grégoire and Soetaert, 2010; Capet et al., 2016), and data assimilation of multi-satellite L3 surface chlorophyll observations, which are available from 1998 and onwards. BAMHBI is coupled online with NEMO using the same version as the near real-time (NRT) product BLKSEA_ANALYSISFORECAST_BGC_007_010. This means that both the biogeochemical and physical processes are simulated in a single run. The surface chlorophyll concentration is assimilated with a daily frequency.

4.1.3. Baltic Sea model

The Baltic Sea biogeochemical reanalysis (Figure 3) with horizontal resolution of 1 nautical mile and 56 vertical levels (BALTICSEA_MULTIYEAR_BGC_003_012) covers the period from January 1993 to December 2021 with a monthly mean output produced by means of the BAL-MFC model system (runs by DMI, Denmark; Spruch et al., 2023). BAL-MFC (based in Neumann

et al., 2015), includes the transport model NEMO v4.0, in combination with the sea ice and thermodynamic model SI3, coupled with the biogeochemical flux model ERGOM and the data assimilation system PDAF for sea surface temperature as well as temperature and salinity profiles. This product has been generated as a one-way online coupled run using a NEMO configuration adapted to the Baltic Sea. Sea surface temperature satellite observations and in-situ profile observations are assimilated into the Nemo analysis field using the PDAF tool every midnight, alternating the assimilation of SST, temperature and salinity profiles every three days.

4.2. Statistical approach and subsampling

To determine the impacts of improved data quality on our ability to confidently establish the existence of trends in environmental data, we use the metric trend detection time (TDT; equation 2). This metric quantifies the number of years of data that is needed to robustly detect a trend in a time series, with a probability of 90% and a confidence level of 95% (Tiao et al., 1990; Weatherhead et al., 1998). The TDT depends on the signal-to-noise ratio in a time series, i.e., the relation between the magnitude of the trend (ω), the standard deviation of the noise (σ_N ; also known as the natural variability), as well as the autocorrelation of the noise (ϕ ; i.e., serial correlation of the noise). This metric expresses the minimum number of years of data needed to detect a robust trend, based on the evaluation of the signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N) in a deseasonalized time series. Importantly, estimating the TDT does not require that a trend has already and unequivocally emerged in the time series; rather it expresses the number of years this will take, based on the existing time dependency and noise level of the evaluated property.

$$TDT = \left(\frac{3.3\sigma_N}{|\omega|} \sqrt{\frac{1+\phi}{1-\phi}} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \quad .2$$

Noise results from both natural variability—associated with red noise, which includes low-frequency phenomena such as slow physical processes and interannual or decadal variability—and data quality, linked to white noise, characterized by independent random noise. The noise's autocorrelation (ranging between -1 and 1) reveals whether it is red noise, indicated by high and persistent autocorrelation and reflecting fluctuations due to internal processes or recurring natural cycles, or white noise, suggested by autocorrelation near zero.

5. Results

Our first baseline analysis evaluates the duration for which repeated monthly measurements are adequate to detect changes arising from natural variability. To understand how varying data quality and coverage influences accuracy of trend estimation, we subsample the time series in two experiments (i) by gathering the data from either the summer or winter season and by (ii) by sampling three random months each year. This is meant to mimic non-

continuous time series often encountered in observational data. The random draw means that certain months are drawn more frequently (Figure 4), which will differ from one region to another due to the length of the time series. However, this draw is preserved for all experiments specific to each region. Thus, three classes of data are evaluated: no-subsampling (M, monthly time series), single season subsampled each year (W, winter; S, summer), three random months subsampled per year (R). In addition, we apply different levels of noise on the full time series and subsampled data, corresponding to best-to-worst expected data quality, and based on the GLODAP adjustment limits described in subsection 2.1. As defined in subsection 4.2, this noise is termed white noise, characterized by unpredictable amplitude and frequency, centered in zero (the noise has equal amounts of positive and negative dispersion around its average equal zero), whose standard deviation is set according to the GLODAP adjustment limits, which defines the boundary values of its normal distribution. The pH values have been perturbed by adding the biases based on the pH measurement, and the resultant noise has been converted to H^+ . As with subsampling, each region - the Mediterranean, Black and Baltic Seas - has its own random draw of noise values. Thus, the data are classified in the other groups: non-perturbed (0), perturbed with the values of adjustment limit (1), twice the adjustment limit (2), and four times the adjustment limit (4). The impact of subsampling and the noise levels on the ability to detect accurate trends is then evaluated using changes in the TDT (equation 1).

Table 1: Nomenclature of grouped data according level of depth, sampling strategy and perturbation level : 1 % in oxygen, 2 % in nitrate, and 0.01 in pH.

Level of depth	Perturbation level	Sample frequency	nomenclature
s: Surface, d: deeper layer	0: Non-perturbed data	M: Monthly, R: Random, S: Summer, W: Winter	s0M, d0M s0R, d0R s0S, d0S s0W, d0W
s: Surface, d: deeper layer	1: perturbed with the values of adjustment limit	M: Monthly, R: Random, S: Summer, W: Winter	s1M, d1M s1R, d1R s1S, d1S s1W, d1W
s: Surface, d: deeper layer	2: twice the adjustment limit	M: Monthly, R: Random, S: Summer, W: Winter	s2M, d2M s2R, d2R s2S, d2S s2W, d2W
s: Surface, d: deeper layer	4: four times the adjustment limit	M: Monthly, R: Random, S: Summer, W: Winter	s4M, d4M s4R, d4R s4S, d4S s4W, d4W

The nomenclature denotes the sample frequency, perturbation level or absence, and sampling depth (for example, ROS for random non-perturbed surface data). The selected depths are based on the vertical location of specific characteristics of each basin in the model and noted “s”, “d”, for the surface, and the deepest level, respectively. For the Mediterranean

these are depths between 0-10 m (s), and 260-270 m (d), which correspond to the surface, and the minimum oxygen level, respectively. The Black Sea sampling takes place between 0-10 m (s), and 50-60 m (d) representing the surface, and the deepest point of the halocline linked with the top of the oxycline, respectively. For the Baltic Sea, samples are taken between 0-10 m (s), and 70-80 m (d), representing the surface, and the depth under the halocline associated with the top of the oxycline, respectively.

Figure 4: Recurrence of each month of the random sampling for a) the Mediterranean Sea, b) the Black Sea, c) the Baltic Sea.

Mapping the results allows us to handle spatial variability that can yield additional unresolved variability to the signal and the noise. However, for the purpose of clarity, not all results will be presented as a map.

5.1. Mediterranean Sea

The number of years of data needed to detect a trend (TDT) in the concentrations of H^+ , oxygen (O_2) and nitrate (NO_3) in the Mediterranean Sea, as well as the ratio of the signal (the magnitude of the trend) to the noise (σ_N ; the natural variability as defined in Section 4.2) are shown in Figure 5. Low TDTs occur in regions where the signal-to-noise ratio is high. Overall, the relatively high signal-to-noise ratio in surface H^+ concentration results in TDTs shorter than 20 years, except in the region of deep-water formation in the Gulf of Lions and in the quasi-permanent anticyclonic gyre to the south of Crete. The TDTs are also somewhat elevated in the Alboran Sea – just east of the Gibraltar Strait, this may result from variability in the inflowing Atlantic waters, which are represented in the model as a boundary condition.

Figure 5: Signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N), and number of years of data needed to distinguish trend from natural variability (year), in the Mediterranean Sea, for hydrogen ion [H^+] (a-d), oxygen [O_2] (e-h), and nitrate [NO_3] (i-l) in based case (no-perturbed monthly time series). The left coupled panel “Base case - surface” (i.e., both (ω/σ_N) and (year)) represents the surface layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 0-10m), and the right coupled panel “Base case - deep” represents the deeper layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 260-270m).

Overall, the detectability of trends varies across different regions of the Mediterranean Sea because of the magnitude of the trends and follows roughly the seven subdivisions of the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM), established with reference to ecotrophic and catch-based indicators for the period 1970-2017 (GFCM-FAO, 2009). In deeper waters, although the natural variability of H^+ is lower than at the surface, the much weaker trend hinders rapid detection of changes in H^+ levels (although in absolute terms the trend remains strong, which explains TDTs of around 35 years in many subregions.). For O_2 and NO_3 trends the situation is the opposite, deep trends are more rapidly detectable than at the surface. This is especially the case in the western basin. In the eastern basin, particularly long TDTs occur in the Adriatic and Aegean Seas, areas of winter deep-water formations (Figure 5 (h and I)).

In the next examples we use the subsampled data and perturbed data to examine impacts on TDTs, allowing an exploration of the interplay between measurement frequency, measurement uncertainty, natural variability, and signal detection in different regions.

In general, and somewhat surprising, both random and seasonal sampling reduces the TDTs compared to full monthly sampling (compare Figures 6 and 5). This occurs because the signal-to-noise ratio is slightly enhanced and because the autocorrelation of the noise is reduced. Both of these factors lower the TDTs (Eq. 2). However, while the direction of the trends is preserved in the random sampling experiment, they are occasionally reversed in the seasonal sampling experiments (for example compare Figure 6 (i and i2) with Figure 5(i)). Therefore, repeated single season sampling cannot be recommended. For instance, in the north-western surface basin, where deep-water formation and mesoscale structures dictate the spatial and temporal distribution of biogeochemical variables, O_2 trends are positive when considering only winter data, while summer sampling yields a negative trend; the opposite result is observed for H^+ . Finally, for both H^+ and NO_3 the spatial patterns of the TDTs in the deep basins remains similar in these subsampling experiments to that of the full monthly sampling, with long TDTs in the east and shorter in the west.

Our third case tests whether the quality of the measurements is a factor in the interpretability and robustness of estimated trends (Figure 7). As described in the introduction of Section 5, three levels of random noise (white noise) have been added to the base case (monthly time series). White noise is added randomly to each of the 12 months in each year. Spatially, the noise value randomly assigned to a given month is identical over the entire domain (each grid point). The disparities between the surface and the deeper layer, observed in the non-perturbed base case (Figure 6), are preserved for all noise levels (M1S, M2S, and M4S; Figure 7).

Figure 6: Signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N), and number of years of data needed to distinguish trend from natural variability (year) for hydrogen ion $[H^+]$ (a-d, m-p, a2-d2), oxygen $[O_2]$ (e-h, q-t, e2-h2), and nitrate $[NO_3]$ (i-l, u-x, i2-l2) using unperturbed data and the various subsampling schemes in the Mediterranean Sea. The left coupled panel (i.e., both ω/σ_N and (year)) represents the surface layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 0-10m), and the right coupled panel represents the deeper layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 260-270m). The top twelve panels (a-l) represent the random sampling strategy; the middle twelve panels (m-x), the winter sampling strategy; and the bottom twelve panels represent the summer sampling strategy (a2-l2).

As data quality drops down from M1 to M4, the signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N) becomes closer to zero, which would increase the TDT. Further, adding white noise changes, in some cases, the magnitude of the trends. For instance, the magnitude of the long-term changes in NO_3 (H^+) has been increased (decreased) in comparison to the base case in the M4S (M4D) experiment, thereby shortening (lengthening) the TDT (Figure 7 (j2 and d2)). However, the addition of randomness in the variability, i.e., white noise also leads to reduce the cyclicity of the total noise. While the effect of larger variability (high dispersion of the noise; σ_N) is to increase the TDT, the effect of lower cyclicity of this variability (lower autocorrelation of the noise; ϕ) is to reduce it (Eq. 2 and Figure 8 (a)). Therefore, comparing the spatial distribution of the TDTs between the base case (Figure 5) and the monthly perturbed data (Figure 7) shows

that there is not a large systematic change in the TDTs as the level of noise in the data is increased; the TDTs distribution in these perturbation experiments are generally consistent with those in the non-perturbed experiments.

Figure 7: Signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N) , and number of years of data needed to distinguish trend from natural variability (year), in the Mediterranean Sea, for hydrogen ion $[H^+]$ (a-d, m-p, a2-d2), oxygen $[O_2]$ (e-h, q-t, e2-h2), and nitrate $[NO_3]$ (i-l, u-x, i2-l2) using perturbed monthly sampling according different levels of noise added to the data. The left coupled panel “Base case – surface” (i.e., (ω/σ_N) and (year)) represents the surface layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 0-10m), and the right coupled panel “Base case - deep” represents the deeper layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 260-270m). M1S-M1D, M2S-M2D, M4s-M4D refer to the classification of the data described in Section 5, M for monthly data, S and D for surface and deeper layer respectively, and (1): perturbed with the values of adjustment limit, (2): twice the adjustment limit, and (4): four times the adjustment limit.

Figure 8: A schematic representation of equation (2) that permit to estimate the Trend Detection Time (TDT) solved for maximum trend (orange isolines), and for mean trend (black line) of $[\text{H}^+]$ estimated at $2.63 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $1.05 \cdot 10^{-5}$, respectively, in the Mediterranean Sea (a). The level of grey in the background represents the TDT estimated using the mean trend. (b) Relationship between the autocorrelation that indicates the randomness (low autocorrelation) or the cyclicity of the noise (high autocorrelation) and the magnitude of the intensity of the variability (the standard deviation composed of white and red noise), for $[\text{H}^+]$ in the Mediterranean Sea. The colored scatterplot indicates the trend detection time according to the cases enumerated in Table 1.

In Figure 9, we assess the data quality according to all the cases of sampling frequency. The least precise data (worst data quality) are those that require the longest time series to distinguish a robust trend. This result is common to all biogeochemical properties, sampling frequencies and depth intervals, with the notable exception of summer sampling of surface NO_3 concentrations. However, as explained above, sampling in a single season can have the effect of drastically altering the magnitude and direction of the trend, which does not reflect the exact trend. Additionally, the effectiveness of sub-sampling, such as random sub-sampling, is reduced or even counter-productive with the degradation of data quality, which makes the long-term signal inaccurate, as illustrated by a longer TDT.

The surface-deeper layer discrepancies are clearly represented in Figure 9, with surface waters requiring longer time series of NO_3 and O_2 than deeper waters, in contrast to H^+ (Figures 5, 6 and 7). Also, the levels of data quality affect TDT differently depending on whether the data come from the surface or deeper layers. Despite increasing variability with data quality degradation, the TDT is almost unchanged or even shortened in some cases, mainly related to the first two levels of white noise added. This arises because data quality degradation can lead to overestimation of trends by amplifying variability, which counterbalances this increase in variability, thus little modifying the signal-to-noise ratio, as in the case of NO_3 and O_2 concentrations (see figure 7). The degradation of data quality can also modify trend estimation by altering the nature of the noise, i.e. its cyclical or random nature. Thus, the addition of (random) white noise can transform the naturally cyclic (i.e. highly autocorrelated) initial variability into a more random variability in such a way as to reduce the sensitivity of the TDT to the amplitude of variability (σ_N), as for deeper layer H^+ concentrations (Figure 8 (a)). Clearly, this reduction in TDT is an artifact of the statistical method's limitations.

Indeed, equation 2 shows that TDT is dependent on the signal, the noise amplitude (i.e. the intensity of the so-called natural variability), as well as the “color” of this noise through the degree of the autocorrelation of this noise, in other words, the origin and nature of this noise. In this way, autocorrelation makes it possible to specify whether the noise is more white, i.e. random and linked to data quality (low autocorrelation, usually below 0.3), or red, i.e. cyclical and predictable, linked to natural phenomena (high autocorrelation, usually above 0.2-0.3).

Figure 9: Relationship between the Trend Detection Time (TDT; year) and the magnitude of the intensity of the variability (the standard deviation composed of white and red noise), for $[H^+]$ the top panel, $[O_2]$ the middle panel, and $[NO_3]$ the bottom panel, in the Mediterranean Sea. The transparent scatterplot represents the base case of the surface data (green) and the deeper layer (blue). The colored circles indicate the levels of perturbation (white noise added), yellow for perturbed with the values of adjustment limit (Noisy 1x AL), orange for twice the adjustment limit (Noisy 2x AL), and red for four times the adjustment limit (Noisy 4x AL). The annotations refer to the classification of the data described in Section 5, M for monthly data, R for random sampling, W for winter sampling, and S for summer sampling.

To better understand the non-linear relation between the TDT and the data quality, a description of the relation between the three main statistical metrics is needed. With this aim we examine the example of H^+ in the Mediterranean Sea. Figure 8b shows that, as noise is added to the data the standard deviation (σ_N) is increased while the autocorrelation of the noise (ϕ) is decreased. However, the greater the amplitude and the cyclicity of the variability (represented by the natural fluctuations σ_N), the more sensitive the TDT will be to changes in the autocorrelation of the noise (less steep isolines in the left part of Figure 8a than in the right). So, although the data are spatially identically disturbed, the reduction in autocorrelation in areas of high natural variability (most often recognized by a very low ω/σ_N ratio) further reduces the TDT, while autocorrelation and natural variability cancel out in areas of low variability and less cyclic (most often recognized by a high ω/σ_N ratio). Finally, we would like to stress that the trend sets the absolute value of the TDT (strong trend correspond to short TDT (orange vs. black isolines), and vice versa) and therefore modulate the extent to which autocorrelation and noise variability cancel each other out (lag of 5 years between the orange isolines vs. 10 years lag for isolines in black).

As autocorrelation is decreased when white noise is added to the data, this means that lower measurement precision clearly will make natural variability, such as associated with climate modes, harder to detect.

5.2. Black Sea

This subsection is dedicated to the Black Sea. Here, we will not detail the theoretical aspects of the TDT to the extent done for the Mediterranean Sea, but rather focus on the main results of our analyses. The base case of the Black Sea is shown in Figure 10. Distinguishing long-term trends from short-term variability in the Black Sea's biogeochemical properties, requires analyzing data over a period around 20 years, and even longer in the deepest layer. This arises because of the large natural variability (Figure 11) that envelops the long-term signal resulting in ω/σ_N ratio close to zero (Figure 10). This means that interannual or even decadal variations dominate the signal, and that the Black Sea is subject to strong cyclical changes that are highly autocorrelated. Spatially, the TDTs are predominantly related to the sea's bathymetry (Figure 2) and large-scale gyres. Longer TDTs occur in shallow ocean regions (less than 200 meters deep) as well as in the center of the gyres. For NO_3 and O_2 concentrations, the discrepancy in TDT between surface and deeper layers contrasts with that observed in the Mediterranean Sea, here the TDTs are longer at depth than at the surface. This reflects the quite substantial variability in the deep Black Sea, an order of magnitude greater than that observed at the surface. For H^+ , the situation is the same as in the Mediterranean Sea because of the very large trend in surface H^+ (compare Figure 10 (a-c) and Figure 5 (a-c)).

It should be noted that the statistical method of the TDT can be limited in areas with high space-time variability of monthly mesoscale eddies, as evidenced by TDT artifacts for H^+ and NO_3 at the surface layer in the central Black Sea, shown in Figure 10 (b and j), where these eddies form.

Figure 10: Signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N) , and number of years of data needed to distinguish trend from natural variability (year), in the Black Sea, for hydrogen ion $[H^+]$ (a-d), oxygen $[O_2]$ (e-h), and nitrate $[NO_3]$ (i-l) in based case (no-perturbed monthly time series). The left coupled panel “Base case - surface” (i.e., both (ω/σ_N) and (year)) represents the surface layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 0-10m), and the right coupled panel “Base case - deep” represents the deeper layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 50-60m).

Figure 11 summarizes the results of the subsampling and data perturbation experiments for the Black Sea. In addition to the unexpected findings observed in the Mediterranean Sea, the base case of the Black Sea reveals that monthly sampling hinders the quick detection of an accurate trend. Both random and winter samplings reduce the TDT of H^+ and oxygen, while NO_3 trends are detected faster with recurrent summer sampling or random sampling, due to the reduction of the autocorrelation of the noise which makes the noise stochastic thus less cyclic. However, we cannot exclude the risk of trend reversal with repeated single season sampling, which is therefore not a recommended sampling strategy.

Once more, data quality experiments show that the higher the data quality, the shorter the TDT (from 1x AL to 4x AL in figure 11). However, exceptions remain. Surprisingly, TDTs of NO_3 concentrations vary mostly due to the sampling strategy, the degree of data quality has limited effect. This is because the variability in this system is very large. In fact, the added noise, based on the GLODAP adjustment limit for NO_3 , is an order of magnitude smaller than the natural variability in the Black Sea. Furthermore, the autocorrelation of the noise of NO_3 concentrations, which is close to 1, is almost not reduced at all when noise is added to the data. However, it should be noted that in the case of deeper layer subsampling of this later case, trend estimation is somewhat affected by the quality of the data, increasing the randomness of noise by degrading data quality, which modifies the detectability of natural cycles.

The other case concerns H^+ concentrations, where the application of the statistical method for estimating TDTs tells us more about the impact of data quality on our ability to assess of climate modes than on the accuracy of the Black Sea acidification trend estimate. Indeed, in this case, unlike NO_3 concentrations, the autocorrelation of the noise decreases with data quality degradation, so that the nature of the noise is totally altered. The cyclic nature of the noise (natural variability) disappears to become predominantly random and less variable

(decreasing σ_N). Due to the initially high natural variability of the region's biogeochemical properties, the recurrence of this noise is prone to be masked by the randomness of the additional white noise. In this case, the additional white noise considerably alters the true values of the natural variability leading to lower TDT. This means that low measurement precision makes it challenging to identify inherent natural cycles within the data, reducing the possibility of filtering the time series of cyclical signals in order to extract trends.

Figure 11: Relationship between the Trend Detection Time (TDT; year) and the magnitude of the intensity of the variability (the standard deviation composed of white and red noise), for $[H^+]$ the top panel, $[O_2]$ the middle panel, and $[NO_3]$ the bottom panel, in the Black Sea. The transparent scatterplot represents the base case of the surface data (green) and the deeper layer (blue). The colored circles indicate the levels of perturbation (white noise added), yellow for perturbed with the values of adjustment limit (Noisy 1x AL), orange for twice the adjustment limit (Noisy 2x AL), and red for four times the adjustment limit (Noisy 4x AL). The annotations refer to the classification of the data described in Section 5, M for monthly data, R for random sampling, W for winter sampling, and S for summer sampling.

5.3. Baltic Sea

The Baltic Sea is the third and final study region in this report, whose signal-to-noise ratios and TDTs, for the three biogeochemical properties discussed above, are shown in Figure 12. Here, the TDTs are shorter in the deeper layer than at the surface, except for H^+ . Thus, the TDT patterns in the Baltic Sea base case is similar to those of the Mediterranean Sea base case.

Figure 12: Signal-to-noise ratio (ω/σ_N), and number of years of data needed to distinguish trend from natural variability (year), in the Baltic Sea, for hydrogen ion [H^+] (a-d), oxygen [O_2] (e-h), and nitrate [NO_3] (i-l) in based case (no-perturbed monthly time series). The left coupled panel “Base case - surface” (i.e., both ω/σ_N and (year)) represents the surface layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 0-10m), and the right coupled panel “Base case - deep” represents the deeper layer (average concentration of biogeochemical variables between 70-80m).

Overall, the detectability of trends in H^+ and NO_3 at the surface follows the surface geostrophic flow resulting in an east-west basin-wide TDT gradient. For O_2 , on the other hand, the TDTs are quite homogenous. In deeper waters, although the natural variability is even higher than at the surface the much stronger trend results in rapid detection of changes in O_2 and NO_3 levels. For H^+ the situation is the opposite, trends are more rapidly detectable at the surface, but the TDT remains high, which largely reflects that the trend is much lower at the surface in addition to high variability.

Figure 13: Relationship between the Trend Detection Time (TDT; year) and the magnitude of the intensity of the variability (the standard deviation composed of white and red noise), for $[H^+]$ the top panel, $[O_2]$ the middle panel, and $[NO_3]$ the bottom panel, in the Baltic Sea. The transparent scatterplot represents the base case of the surface data (green) and the deeper layer (blue). The colored circles indicate the levels of perturbation (white noise added), yellow for perturbed with the values of adjustment limit (Noisy 1x AL), orange for twice the adjustment limit (Noisy 2x AL), and red for four times the adjustment limit (Noisy 4x AL). The annotations refer to the classification of the data described in Section 5, M for monthly data, R for random sampling, W for winter sampling, and S for summer sampling.

All the sampling frequency and their respective level of perturbation (best: base case -to- worst: 4x AL) are depicted in Figure 13. It is clear from this dataset that the higher the variability (standard deviation), the greater the TDT, and that in general, the variability of biogeochemical properties in the Baltic Sea is high. Estimation of this variability depends on the choice of sampling depth and frequency, and on the quality of the data. At the surface,

H^+ and O_2 show increasing variability as data quality deteriorates, resulting in a longer TDT than the base case. On the other hand, random sampling of these two biogeochemical properties is beneficial to a shorter TDT. Indeed, random sampling avoids capturing certain low-frequency cyclic phenomena in the signal. Here again, even if single-season sampling reduces the TDT in most cases, it may bias trend estimation. The H^+ in deeper layer is notably distinct; it aligns with the condition observed in the Black Sea in this context. The nature of the noise is strongly modified, its cyclic and highly variable aspect is strongly diminished by the addition of white noise of a stochastic nature, which underrepresents the variability in the system. NO_3 presents the same situation as in the Black Sea, i.e. data quality has a limited effect on variability and TDT, conversely to sampling frequency. As in the Black Sea, the noise added to NO_3 concentrations is at least one order of magnitude smaller than the natural variability in the Baltic Sea. Moreover, this white noise is unable to reduce the high autocorrelation of the initial data noise.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The science case of EuroGO-SHIP highlighted the different factors that need to be considered to accurately estimate trends in acidification via H^+ concentrations, eutrophication via NO_3 , and deoxygenation via O_2 concentrations. To this end, the statistical method of trend detection time was used, and its various metrics were analyzed to better understand the factors acting on trends, natural variability and the nature of the noise itself. This method was performed using reanalysis data as the 'known-truth' for long term change and variability of ocean properties.

It is crucial to consider each region independently to determine the length of the time series required for an accurate estimate of trends. Indeed, the Black Sea seems to require one of the longest time series at the surface, followed in descending order by the Baltic Sea, and then the Mediterranean Sea. Local factors, such as mesoscale eddies, deep-water formation, and even bathymetry, as in the Black Sea, must be considered when choosing measurement stations. It is therefore recommended to favor repeated section measurements rather than fixed-location stations to provide more accurate overview and avoid erroneous estimation and interpretation of trends due to local or subregional factors.

Each biogeochemical property requires a different length of time series, whether trends are to be observed at the surface or in deeper layers. Apart from the Black Sea, it is recommended to estimate trends on time series longer than 20 years in the surface layers so that the trend emerges from the background natural variability. This recommendation applies below the halocline in the Black Sea.

The most striking results of this study concern data quality and sampling frequency, which are two key factors affecting the accurate detectability of trends and climate modes. High data quality is essential in any case. It shortens the length of the time series needed to estimate accurate trends, when natural variability is relatively low. In the case of high variability, high

data quality enables the natural variability to be correctly represented, and therefore the data to be correctly filtered in order to extract the trend.

Finally, it should be noted that random sampling can avoid capturing the cyclic noise that defines natural variability, and therefore reduce TDT. However, this is not without risk for errors in trend estimation, if real natural variability is high. However, it is imperative that this approach be used in conjunction with high data quality to reduce the risk of error.

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